
SCREENING COWPEA (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walpers) LINES FOR RESISTANCE TO SOME VIRUSES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Thirty-three Cowpea lines were screened in a greenhouse at Ibadan, southwest Nigeria for response to four cowpea viruses, namely the *bean common mosaic Potyvirus-blackeye* Cowpea strain (BCMV-BIC), *Cowpea aphid-borne mosaic Potyvirus* (CABMV), *Cowpea Mottle Carmovirus* (CMeV) and *southern bean mosaic Sobemovirus* (SBMV). Disease severity was scored from; 1=no infection, to 5=very severe infection. Symptomless lines were serologically tested with protein-A sandwich enzyme- linked immunosorbent assay (PAS-ELISA) to distinguish lines with latent infection from the non-infected lines. Nine Cowpea lines were severely or very severely infected by the four viruses. Three viruses namely BCMV-BIC, CABMV and SBMV-BIC did not infect two lines (IT90K-284-2 and IT82D-889). In addition, CABMV and BCMV-BIC did not infect the cowpea varieties IT85F-2687 and Futo Coiled. SBMV and BCMV-BIC did not cause infection on CP-VAR8. No infection in some Cowpea lines indicated resistance to the virus and such lines are potential breeding materials for elite varieties. The incidence of BCMV-BIC infection was 100% in 13 lines, CABMV infection in 9, CMeV in 15 and SBMV in 3.

KEYWORDS: Cowpea, Cowpea virus, Resistance, Breeding material, ELISA

INTRODUCTION

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* Walpers) is an important staple food crop in sub-Saharan Africa, especially in Nigeria where the bulk of it is produced and consumed (Singh et al., 2000). More than 5.4million tons of dried cowpea are produced worldwide, with Africa producing nearly 5.2million. Nigeria, the largest producer and consumer, accounts for about 61% production in Africa and 58% worldwide. The seeds of cowpea contain about 25% protein and form a major source of plant proteins, vitamins to man and feed to animals, while the young leaves and immature pods are eaten as vegetables. Cowpea's high protein content, its adaptability to different soil types and intercropping systems, resistance to drought, ability to improve soil fertility by symbiotically fixing atmospheric nitrogen, and prevention of erosion when used as a cover crop makes it an important economic crop in many developing countries. However cowpea yields are low averaging between 100 and 300kg ha^{-1} due to constraints such as weather, parasitic weeds or insects and diseases amongst others.

A great number of pests and diseases attack Cowpea at all growth stages, and are without doubt, the most limiting factor affecting intensive Cowpea production in tropical Africa, as they may cause total grain loss (Emechebe et al., 1991, Jackai and Adalla, 1997). Several studies have shown that viral diseases cause serious economic losses to cowpea crop by reducing yields and crop quality (Kaiser and Mossahebbi, 1975, Bozarth and Shoyinka, 1979, Byoung-Cheorl et al., 2005). According to Vander borght and Baudoin (2001), more than twenty viruses have been observed worldwide in cultivated cowpea, nine of which occur in Sub-Saharan Africa and Nigeria (Taiwo and Shoyinka, 1988). The economically important ones include *cowpea aphid-borne mosaic virus* (CABMV), *cowpea mosaic virus* (CPMV) genus *Comovirus* and occasionally *Southern bean mosaic virus* (SBMV) genus *Sobemovirus*. *Blackeye cowpea mosaic virus* (BICMV) has a low rate of occurrence but may be widespread in some northern states (Alegbejo and Kashina, 2001), while others are of localized importance or unimportant (Thottappilly and Rossel, 1992, Shoyinka et al., 1997). The techniques used to control these diseases include the use of virus-free seeds, timely planting to avoid the vectors, crop rotation, eradication of weeds hosting the virus or the vector, establishment of barriers to prevent the movement of vectors, application of insecticides to control the vector population and the use of resistant varieties.

Although appropriate agronomic and cultural practices may be adopted to reduce yield losses due to viral infection, the most economical, practicable effective and environment friendly method of control of legume viruses in Nigeria is through the use of resistant varieties (Taiwo,2003). Some legume lines with individual or combined resistance to several viruses have been identified; for soybean (Lim, 1982, Lim, 1985) and cowpea (Thottappilly and Rossel, 1992).Because

breeding and release of new varieties is a continuous process, it is necessary to continuously screen lines with potential for use as sources of resistance to current and emerging pests. The objective of this study was to identify some cowpea lines tolerant or resistant to four viruses as a basic step in a virus resistance breeding programme.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thirty-three cowpea lines consisting of eleven (11) advanced cultivars, sixteen (16) breeding lines and six (6) landraces (Table 1), were screened for response to the following four seed-transmitted viruses in a greenhouse at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, southwest Nigeria:

- a) *Cowpea aphid-borne mosaic virus* (CABMV)
- b) *Bean common mosaic potyvirus-blackeye cowpea strain* (BCMV-BIC)
- c) *Cowpea mottle Carmovirus* (CMeV)
- d) *Southern bean mosaic Sobemovirus*.

Isolates of the viruses were collected from the virology unit, IITA, Ibadan and maintained in Ife Brown variety. In each variety, five seeds were sown per pot in 10 Stewart's 8" plant pots, filled with loamy soil sterilized with cypermethrin 10% E.C. to eliminate soil inhabiting microorganisms, and enriched with farmyard manure. Seedlings were thinned to two per pot, two weeks after planting, constantly watered and kept weed-free by hand pulling, when necessary. At the emergence of the first trifoliolate leaf, twenty seedlings of each variety were mechanically inoculated with isolates of the viruses. The inoculums of the viruses were prepared by grinding infected leaves of young plants with sterilized mortars and pestles in buffer of 0.05M dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate (K_2HPO_4), pH 7.5 at a ratio of 1:2 (tissue weight: buffer volume). Leaf surfaces of plants to be inoculated were dusted with Carborundum powder (180 grit) and pestles were used to apply the inoculums. Hands were washed thoroughly with detergent between treatments to avoid contamination, and all inoculated plants were rinsed with clean water after inoculation and kept in a greenhouse with temperatures at 25-28^oc.

Scoring of disease severity was by visual means using a 5-point scale; 1= no infection (i.e. no symptom was observed on the leaves and ELISA result was negative), 2 = light infection (0 -20% of the leaves expressed symptoms and ELISA result of symptomless plants was positive), 3 = moderate infection (symptoms appeared on 21 -40% of the leaves), 4 = severe infection (symptoms appeared on 41 -60% of the leaves), 5 = very severe infection (symptoms appeared on more than 60% of the leaves). The incidence of infection was taken as the proportion of infected plants to the total number of plants in the 10 pots. Symptomless plants were tested for presence of viruses using protein-A sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (PAS-ELISA), described by Hughes and Thomas (1988). Polyclonal antiserum to the viruses was obtained from the virology unit, IITA, Ibadan.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that all the cowpea lines/cultivars used in this investigation were susceptible to at least one of the cowpea viruses studied. These viruses caused systemic symptoms to the diseased plants, the most common being mosaics, mottling, distorted and crinkled leaves, as well as defoliation and reduced pod formation. In addition, three of the viruses, namely BCMV-BIC, CABMV, and CMeV caused stunting or dwarfing and premature death in some severe and very severely infected cowpea lines and/or cultivars (Table 2). Similar symptoms have been reported elsewhere on legumes infected by viral diseases (Bock, 1973, Hampton et al., 1997, Vanderborgh and Baudoin, 2001). There was considerable variation in susceptibility to viral infection between the plants materials used in the study. Among the advanced cultivars, Ife brown, IT82D-716, IT84S-2246-4, IT87D-784-1, IT96D-774, IT97K-499-38, TVu 12349 and TVX 3236 were susceptible to all four cowpea viral diseases and consequently, have no potential as breeding materials for elite varieties resistant to these viruses. On the contrary, IT82D-889 was infected only by CMeV, IT86D-317 by CABMV and CMeV, and IT86D-880 by CMeV and SBMV. These cultivars may be used to confer resistance on elite varieties for the different viruses they are tolerant of. In addition, the exploitation of cowpea genotypes with multiple gene resistance could offer a better option in the breeding work to control several viruses so as to circumvent the escalating problems of viruses and ultimately yield. Among the 16 breeding lines evaluated, only three, namely IT85F-2687, IT86D-1010 and IT90K-284-2, and two landraces (Futo Coiled and TVu 13686), hold promise for breeding for resistance to CABMV which is the most economically important cowpea viral disease in Nigeria.

Table 1: Status of cowpea lines used in the study and their sources.

S/N	Genotype	Status	Source
1	Ife brown	Advanced cultivar	Virology unit, IITA
2	IT82D-716	Advanced cultivar	GRU,IITA
3	IT82D-889	Advanced cultivar	GRU,IITA
4	IT84S-2246-4	Advanced cultivar	GRU,IITA
5	IT86D-371	Advanced cultivar	GRU,IITA
6	IT86D-880	Advanced cultivar	GRU,IITA
7	IT87D-784-1	Advanced cultivar	GRU,IITA
8	IT96D-774	Advanced cultivar	Virology unit, IITA
9	IT97K-499-38	Advanced cultivar	Virology unit, IITA
10	TVu 12349	Advanced cultivar	Virology unit, IITA
11	TVX3236	Advanced cultivar	Virology unit, IITA
12	ART91-2	Breeding line	Virology lab., IAR & T, Moor plantation, Ibadan
13	CP-VAR8	Breeding line	CPEB, UI,Ibadan
14	IAR48	Breeding line	Virology lab., IAR & T, Moor plantation
15	IAR72	Breeding line	Virology lab., IAR & T
16	IT83D-442	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
17	IT85F-2687	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
18	IT85F-867-5	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
19	IT86D-1010	Breeding line	GRU, IITA
20	IT86D-719	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
21	IT89KD-775	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
22	IT90K-284-2	Breeding line	GRU, IITA
23	IT95K-1093-5	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
24	IT96D-740	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
25	IT97K-1068-7	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
26	IT97K-491-2	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
27	TVu 66	Breeding line	Virology unit, IITA
28	Futo Coiled	Landrace	CPEB, UI, Ibadan
29	Solojo 2	Landrace	CPEB,UI, Ibadan
30	Solojo 4	Landrace	CPEB, UI, Ibadan
31	TVu 11426	Landrace	CPEB, UI, Ibadan
32	TVu 1190	Landrace	CPEB, UI, Ibadan
33	TVu 13686	Landrace	CPEB, UI, Ibadan

Latency was observed in Futo coiled and Solojo 2 infected with CMV, IT86D-1010 infected with BCMV-BIC, TVu 11426 and TVu 1190 infected with CABMV, and IT85F-2687 and TVu 11426 infected with SBMV (Table 2). These varieties could be used to breed for tolerance to these cowpea viruses. None of the varieties studied expressed no infection to the four viruses simultaneously, but IT86D-719, IT96D-740, Ife brown, IT82D-716 and IT84S-2246-4 were all very severely infected by all the viruses studied. Three viruses (BCMV-BIC, CABMV and SBMV) did not infect varieties IT90K-284-2 and IT82D-889, suggesting that these varieties are potential breeding materials for the three viruses

Table 2: Response of cowpea lines to infection by four cowpea viruses in a greenhouse.

S/N	Varieties/Lines	BCMV-BIC	CABMV	CMeV	SBMV
1	Ife brown	SS, SD, N	SS, SD	SS	SS, CH
2	IT82D-716	SS	SS, CH	SS, SD	LL
3	IT82D-889	-	-	SS, CH	-
4	IT84S-2246-4	SS, CH	SS, CH	SS, SD	SS
5	IT86D-317	-	SS	SS	-
6	IT86D-880	-	-	SS, CH	LL
7	IT87D-784-1	SS	SS, CH	SS, CH	SS
8	IT96D-774	SS, CH	SS	SS, SD	SS
9	IT97K-499-38	SS, SD, N	SS, SD	SS	SS
10	TVu 12349	SS	SS, CH	SS	SS
11	TVX 3236	SS, SD, CH, N	SS, SD, CH	SS, SD	SS
12	ART 91-2	SS, SD	SS, SD	SS, N	SS
13	CP-VAR8	SS	SS	-	-
14	IAR 48	SS, N	SS, CH	SS, N	SS, CH
15	IAR 72	SS, N	SS, CH	SS, N	SS, CH
16	IT83D-442	SS, SD	SS, SD	SS, SD	SS
17	IT85F-2687	-	-	SS	LI
18	IT85F-867-5	SS, N	SS, SD, CH	SS	SS
19	IT86D-1010	LI	-	LI	SS
20	IT86D-719	SS, CH	SS	SS, SD	LL
21	IT89KD-775	SS, SD	SS,SD	SS	SS
22	IT90K-284-2	-	-	SS, SD	-
23	IT95K-1093-5	SS, SD	SS	SS	-
24	IT96D-740	SS, SD	SS, CH	SS	SS
25	IT97K-1068-7	SS, SD	SS, CH	SS	-
26	IT97K-491-2	SS, SD	SS, SD	SS,CH	SS, CH
27	TVu 66	SS, SD	SS	SS,SD	SS
28	Futo coiled	-	-	LI	LL
29	Solojo 2	SS, CH, N	SS	LI	LL
30	Solojo 4	SS, SD	SS	SS	SS
31	TVu 11426	SS	LI	SS, SD	LI
32	TVu 1190	SS, SD	LI	SS	SS
33	TVu 13686	SS, SD	-	SS, SD	SS

CH =Chlorosis; LI = Latent Infection; LL =Local Lesion; SS = Systemic Symptoms; N = Necrosis; SD =Stunting/Dwarfing; - = No Infection. BCMV-BIC= Bean common potyvirus-blackeye cowpea strain; CABMV= Cowpea aphid-borne mosaic virus; CMeV= Cowpea mottle carmovirus; SBMV= Southern bean mosaic sobemovirus

The incidence and severity of cowpea viral infection differed widely amongst the varieties (Table 3). The incidence of infection ranged from 0 to 100%. The incidence of BCMV-BIC infection was 100% in five advanced cultivars, seven breeding lines and one landrace, while the corresponding values for CABMV were four each for advanced cultivars and breeding lines, and none for landraces. Across all cultivars evaluated, the incidence of BCMV-BIC, CABMV, CMeV and SBMV was respectively 69.1, 63.1, 74.9 and 47.4%. The low incidence of SBMV might suggest the inability of its vector to thrive under the conditions of the experiment.

Table 3: Severity and incidence of four viral diseases on some cowpea varieties in the greenhouse.

S/N	Variety	BCMV-BIC		CABMV		CMeV		SBMV	
		Severity	Incidence	Severity	Incidence	Severity	Incidence	Severity	Incidence
1	Ife brown	5	100.0	5	100.0	3	100.0	5	86.7
2	IT82D-716	5	100.0	3	57.1	5	100.0	5	87.5
3	IT82D-889	1	0.0	1	0.0	3	60.0	1	0.0
4	IT84S-2246-4	5	100.0	5	100.0	5	100.0	4	92.9
5	IT86D-317	1	0.0	2	12.5	4	77.8	1	0.0
6	IT86D-880	1	0.0	1	0.0	5	100.0	3	58.3
7	IT87D-784-1	3	58.3	4	63.6	5	100.0	4	92.9
8	IT96D-774	5	93.3	4	100.0	5	100.0	3	66.7
9	IT97K-449-38	5	100.0	5	100.0	4	100.0	3	37.5
10	TVu 12349	5	61.5	4	92.3	2	33.3	2	43.8
11	TVX 3236	5	100.0	4	100.0	4	66.7	3	77.8
12	ART 91-2	3	83.3	5	100.0	3	54.5	2	27.3
13	CP-VAR8	5	71.4	5	73.3	1	0.0	1	0.0
14	IAR 48	4	100.0	5	77.8	3	60.0	2	50.0
15	IAR 72	5	100.0	2	87.5	5	100.0	4	100.0
16	IT83D-442	4	100.0	3	85.7	2	66.7	2	14.3
17	IT85F-2687	1	0.0	1	0.0	2	28.6	2	20.0
18	IT85F-867-5	5	88.9	2	77.8	2	50.0	3	28.5
19	IT86D-1010	2	16.6	1	0.0	5	100.0	2	40.0
20	IT86D-719	4	100.0	4	63.6	3	83.3	4	91.7
21	IT89KD-775	3	55.5	3	85.7	3	88.9	3	60.0
22	IT90K-284-2	1	0.0	1	0.0	4	100.0	1	0.0
23	IT95K-1093-5	5	90.9	4	91.7	4	100.0	1	0.0
24	IT96D-740	5	90.0	5	88.9	5	100.0	2	23.5
25	IT97K-1068-7	5	100.0	3	100.0	4	100.0	1	0.0
26	IT97K-491-2	5	100.0	5	100.0	5	100.0	3	33.3
27	TVu 66	5	100.0	5	100.0	3	64.3	4	83.0
28	Futo Coiled	1	0.0	1	0.0	4	81.8	3	40.0
29	Solojo 2	5	61.5	5	64.3	2	33.3	5	100.0
30	Solojo 4	4	54.5	4	85.7	2	14.3	3	80.0
31	TVu 11426	3	63.6	2	66.7	3	25.0	2	20.0
32	TVu 1190	5	100.0	2	7.1	2	83.3	2	9.1
33	TVu 13686	4	90.9	1	0.0	5	100.0	4	100.0

1=no infection; 2=light infection; 3=moderate infection; 4=severe infection; 5=very severe infection

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